

ANALYTICAL MODELLING OF LAMINATED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A significant number of research articles has been published on the analytical modelling of composite laminates over the past twenty years. The drive for more accurate analysis has led us to techniques which have become more and more computationally burdensome; while the engineering world continues to use simple, first order shear deformable plate theory as its primary tool. This paper presents a unique approach to the analysis of thick laminated composites by presenting two simple finite element methods. The first uses the Predictor Corrector technique to extend the simple Mindlin type element to achieve greater accuracy, and the second develops a new Least Squares element which can approximate a C^1 continuous element. The Least Squares element has the capability to incorporate a simplified higher order basis into a piecewise continuous displacement field creating an accurate, yet computationally simple, element. These two methods have the potential to significantly upgrade analysis methods with little additional computational cost. It is hoped that this work can instigate further research into efficient modelling of composite laminates.

1 Introduction

Laminated fiber reinforced composite plates (LFRCP's) are providing engineers with the ability to design and build structures as never before; however, today's technology has only begun to realize the resource that is becoming available in the field of composite materials. As the field continues to grow, so must the ability to perform accurate engineering analyses. The inherently complex nature of composite laminates often necessitates complex mathematical models which are difficult to implement in practical engineering analysis. Therefore, the need for accurate, yet efficient, methods will remain high. The future calls not only for increased understanding and more accurate modeling of composite materials but also for fresh ideas and approaches on how to effectively and economically predict laminate behavior. This work presents some novel approaches which will provide simple, yet powerful, tools to be used in engineering design analysis. In addition, it may possibly initiate a new methodology for future work in laminated composite plates and shells.

1.1 Evaluation of Current Analyses Methodologies

When solving the LFRCP problem we must make certain assumptions and follow some general guidelines. It is assumed that the layers of the laminate are perfectly bonded together so that no slip can occur between them. In addition, the three displacements, $u_i(x_j)$, must be continuous in x_j to satisfy compatibility, but they need not have a unique $u_{i,3}$ across the lamina interfaces. (Here x_j represents the

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three coordinate directions, $i, j = 1, 2, 3$ and the comma denotes partial differentiation.) This statement is supported by exact, 3- D analysis published by Pagano (1969) [24] and (1970) [25].

Also, it is well accepted that transverse shear effects must be included in thick LFRCP analysis. A first order shear deformable plate theory (SDPT), or Mindlin type theory, is by far the most popular analysis technique to accomplish this task; however, many works have been published in an attempt to overcome some of the deficiencies of this theory. (Mainly the need for a shear correction factor.) A large number of works has concentrated upon trying to gain more accuracy by carrying more terms in the series expansion of the displacements. In other words, a higher order (in the thickness coordinate) SDPT is used. The disadvantage of the higher order approach is that the number of unknowns in the problem quickly becomes large. In addition, it becomes difficult to physically understand and to prescribe boundary conditions for these additional terms. A few of the works in this area have been published by Nelson and Lorch (1974) [20], Lo et al (1977) [12, 13], Kant et al (1988) [7], Murty and Vellaichamy (1987) [19], Pandya and Kant (1988) [26], Mallikarjuna and Kant (1989) [14, 6], Mottram (1989) [16] and Murty (1977) [17]. Simplifications of the higher order approaches are also quite common in current research. The number of unknowns in the displacement field can be reduced by four by setting the transverse stresses on the top and bottom surfaces of the plate equal to zero. The drawback to the simplified approach is that a C^1 continuity requirement arises. Some examples of simplified higher order approaches can be found in works published by Reddy (1984) [29, 28], Kant and Pandya (1988) [5], Senthilnathan et al (1988) [33, 11], Reddy and Phan (1985) [31], Murty (1987) [18] and Khdeir (1989) [8].

The higher order approaches theoretically make sense, but outside the realm of isotropic materials, carrying a finite number of higher order terms does not coincide with the physics of the problem. A higher order SDPT maintains a unique $u_{i,3}$ across the layer interface. The advantage is that a traction free condition on the top and bottom surfaces can be satisfied, and the need for a shear correction coefficient (SCC) is *reduced*. Note the above emphasis on the word *reduced*. Since the assumed deformation field is not exact, then the calculated transverse strain energy is going to deviate from the true energy, and an SCC would be beneficial to adjust this difference. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that the first order SDPT with the *correct* SCC's can give as good, if not better, results for certain cases than a higher order theory without any correction.

Another common analysis method, which follows the physics of the problem, is the discrete layer approach. A piecewise linear (or higher order) field is established within each layer. The obvious drawback to such an approach is that a problem can quickly become intractable for thick plates with a large number of layers. A few of the works published in this area include those by Srinivas (1973) [34], Reddy et al (1989) [30], Barbero and Reddy (1990) [3] and Alam and Asnani (1984) [1, 2]. The discrete layer approach can be simplified by enforcing displacement continuity, as well as transverse traction continuity, at the layer interfaces. In this manner the number of unknowns becomes independent of the number of layers. A few examples of the simplified discrete layer approach include Sciuva (1987) [32], Mawenya and Davies (1974) [15] and Lee et al (1990) [10].

1.2 Analysis Approach

As discussed above in Section 1.1 the first order SDPT has the potential to provide accurate results as long as the correct SCC's can be calculated. In this paper we will develop modifications to a standard first order SDPT finite element program to include the calculation of accurate SCC's. This will be done by comparing the first order transverse strain energy to the *true* strain energy. The true strain energy will be found using the transverse stresses determined by integrating the equations of equilibrium through the thickness of the plate.

The second part of this work will develop a new Least Squares (LS) finite element. The LS method will allow displacements to approximate C^1 continuous functions on the boundaries of the element. With this element we can take advantage of displacement functions which normally would require C^1 continuous interpolation functions. The LS element can be applied to either a simplified higher order approach or a simplified discrete layer approach with a simplified higher order function as the basis for the displacement field. The latter will be used to demonstrate the technique.

Both of the above analysis will be demonstrated by using the finite element method to solve the vibration problem.

2 An Improved First Order Shear Deformation Theory

In this part of the work we will modify a finite element model, based upon a first order SDPT, to include the ability to calculate accurate SCC's for any particular laminate. With accurate SCC's, the first order SDPT will give very good results. This technique, called the Predictor Corrector (PC) technique, has been successfully applied analytically by Noor and Peters (1989) [23] and Noor and Burton (1989) [21], (1990) [22], but implementation of the technique into a finite element analysis has not been published.

One method to obtain SCC's is to equilibrate the calculated transverse strain energy to the actual strain energy. We will compare the strain energy based on the first order theory, $U_{\alpha z}$, to that found using calculated transverse stresses, $\bar{U}_{\alpha z}$. (Here $\alpha = 1, 2$.) If we let k_{α}^o be the original SCC's, then updated coefficients, k_{α} , are found through the relation

$$(k_{\alpha})^2 \bar{U}_{\alpha z} = (k_{\alpha}^o)^2 U_{\alpha z} \quad (1)$$

The calculated transverse stresses are found by rearranging and integrating the equations for 3-D equilibrium. The resulting equations are

$$\sigma_{iz}(z) = \int_{-h/2}^z (\rho \ddot{u}_i - \sigma_{ix,x} - \sigma_{iy,y} - f_i) dz \quad (2)$$

where f_i are any body forces present. The first two of these equations provide us with a method to calculate the transverse stresses σ_{xz} and σ_{yz} . Once this is done, the third provides us with an expression for σ_{zz} , if so desired. However, to perform this integration we must accurately determine the in-plane stresses and then their derivatives.

2.1 Finite element implementation

The basis for the PC finite element model is a standard Mindlin, eight noded, quadratic, isoparametric element utilizing displacements of the form

$$u = u_o + z\phi_x \quad (3)$$

$$v = v_o + z\phi_y \quad (4)$$

$$w = w_o \quad (5)$$

giving five degrees of freedom (u_o , v_o , w_o , ϕ_x and ϕ_y) at each node for a total of forty. In a standard finite element implementation, the stresses are normally calculated from the strains which are found by differentiating the displacements comprised of the nodal displacements. Once the stresses are known throughout the plate, their derivatives could be found. Unfortunately, since a quadratic element was chosen for this analysis, the displacements within an element will, at best, be quadratic and after differentiation will result in linear stresses. The required additional differentiation leaves us with constant stress gradients and, as a result, constant strain energy throughout the element (in certain directions).

Therefore, we will have a mismatch when we compare this strain energy to the strain energy calculated using the first order theory, which results in a quadratic distribution. To alleviate this problem, a technique has been developed to first globally smooth the nodal displacements to a higher order polynomial.

The smoothing technique uses a cubic least squares curve fit routine to calculate the four polynomial coefficients for w , ϕ_x and ϕ_y on each side of the element. In the end, we end up with the coefficient data for twelve cubic curves for each element. The curve fitting is done utilizing five points per side. We use the original three nodal points plus two additional ones. For interior elements a data point from the elements on either side is taken. For boundary elements, two points from the adjacent interior element are used. After this is completed, the next step is to temporarily *transform* our eight noded quadratic element into a twelve noded cubic element. The shape functions associated with both the eight and twelve noded elements can be found in any standard finite element text.

Next, we proceed to build an element displacement vector, $\{\Delta\}_c$, consisting of sixty terms (5 degrees of freedom at each of 12 nodes). The vector is defined as

$$\{\Delta\}_c^T = [(u_o)_1 \quad (v_o)_1 \quad (w_o)_1 \quad (\phi_x)_1 \quad (\phi_y)_1 \quad \dots \quad (\phi_y)_{12}] \quad (6)$$

where the subscript c denotes the cubic element. In building $\{\Delta\}_c$, the original displacements are retained for the corner nodes, and the values for the side nodes are calculated using the polynomial curve fits. In this manner, the displacements which originally varied quadratically, now vary cubically.

Next, the stresses are first calculated at the twelve nodes. We start by finding the strains from the derivatives of displacements at each node by establishing

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{c} \epsilon_o \\ \kappa \end{array} \right\} = [\beta] \{\Delta\} \quad (7)$$

where $[\beta]$ is the standard matrix to include the derivatives of the shape functions. It is important to remember that eqn (7) provides the midplane strains and curvatures at a specific point in the element. The three in-plane strains at this point can be represented as a function of z by

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{c} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{array} \right\} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & z & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & z & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & z \end{bmatrix} [\beta] \{\Delta\} \\ = [Z] [\beta] \{\Delta\} \quad (8)$$

The stresses at this specific point in the plate's thickness become

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{c} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \sigma_{xy} \end{array} \right\} = [Q]_k [Z] [\beta] \{\Delta\} \quad (9)$$

where $[Q]_k$ represents the reduced stiffness coefficients for the k th layer of the laminate, and z falls in this layer. Thus, eqn (9) allows us to calculate the stress at a specific η, ξ, z location in the element.

Stress gradients follow after choosing a convenient set of points at which to determine our desired parameters. Through experimentation and ease of computational implementation, it was found best to use eight interior points coinciding to the Gauss integration points for a three by three integration, (the center point is discarded). The stresses, as given by eqn (9), are calculated as a function of z at each of these eight interior points. The result is established in matrix notation as:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{c} (\sigma)_1 \\ (\sigma)_2 \\ \vdots \\ (\sigma)_8 \end{array} \right\} = \left\{ \begin{array}{c} \left\{ \begin{array}{c} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \sigma_{xy} \end{array} \right\}_1 \\ \vdots \\ \left\{ \begin{array}{c} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \sigma_{xy} \end{array} \right\}_8 \end{array} \right\} \quad (10)$$

Turning our attention now to the derivatives of the stresses, we find the derivatives with respect to the local coordinates at the at any point using the shape functions of the *reduced* element. This is written as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{xx,\eta} \\ \sigma_{xx,\xi} \\ \sigma_{yy,\eta} \\ \sigma_{yy,\xi} \\ \sigma_{xy,\eta} \\ \sigma_{xy,\xi} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} N_{1,\eta} & 0 & 0 & N_{2,\eta} & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ N_{1,\xi} & 0 & 0 & N_{2,\xi} & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & N_{1,\eta} & 0 & 0 & N_{2,\eta} & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & N_{1,\xi} & 0 & 0 & N_{2,\xi} & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & N_{1,\eta} & 0 & 0 & N_{2,\eta} & \cdots & N_{8,\eta} \\ 0 & 0 & N_{1,\xi} & 0 & 0 & N_{2,\xi} & \cdots & N_{8,\xi} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} (\sigma)_1 \\ (\sigma)_2 \\ \vdots \\ (\sigma)_8 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Through the use of the inverse of the Jacobian, we can now get an expression for the derivatives of stresses with respect to the global coordinates at any η, ξ as a function of z . The result is:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{xx,x} \\ \sigma_{yy,y} \\ \sigma_{xy,x} \\ \sigma_{xy,y} \end{Bmatrix} = [\Gamma][N] \begin{Bmatrix} (\sigma)_1 \\ (\sigma)_2 \\ \vdots \\ (\sigma)_8 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

where the rectangular matrices with the Jacobian terms and the derivatives of the shape functions have been represented by $[\Gamma]$ and $[N]$ respectively.

The representation of the body forces, or the dynamic terms, is the final item required before the integration of eqn (2) can be performed. For the case of free vibration we can express the required acceleration terms as:

$$\ddot{u}_\alpha = -\omega^2 (u_{\alpha 0} + z\phi_\alpha) \quad \ddot{w} = -\omega^2 w_0 \quad (13)$$

These equations, once multiplied by mass, are the final expressions we need to calculate the transverse stress distributions through eqn (2).

2.2 Shear correction coefficient calculations

The above discussion provides the appropriate expressions to place into eqn (2) so that the integration can be accomplished. The integration can be performed numerically using a trapezoidal rule, or other simple integration method, starting at $z = -h/2$ with σ_{xz} and σ_{yz} equal to zero or to whatever surface tractions exist. The final values of σ_{xz} and σ_{yz} at $z = h/2$ should correspond to the tractions on the top surface of the plate, which are zero for the free vibration case. The end results of the calculations are the determinations of the transverse shear distributions through the thickness of the plate at some specific η, ξ location.

The transverse strain energy densities calculated using the first order theory are defined by

$$U_{\alpha z} = \frac{1}{2} C_{\alpha z} \gamma_{\alpha z}^2 \quad (14)$$

where

$$C_{xz} = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \bar{C}_{44} dz \quad C_{yz} = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \bar{C}_{55} dz \quad (15)$$

and γ_{xz} and γ_{yz} are given by the strain displacement relations.

The transverse strain energies derived through the equations of equilibrium are defined by:

$$\bar{U}_{xz} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \bar{C}_{44} (\bar{\gamma}_{xz}^2) dz \quad (16)$$

$$\bar{U}_{yz} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \bar{C}_{55} (\bar{\gamma}_{yz}^2) dz \quad (17)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{\gamma}_{xz} &= S_{44}\sigma_{xz} + S_{45}\sigma_{yz} \\ \bar{\gamma}_{yz} &= S_{54}\sigma_{xz} + S_{55}\sigma_{yz}\end{aligned}$$

Here

$$\begin{bmatrix} S_{44} & S_{45} \\ S_{54} & S_{55} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{44} & \bar{Q}_{45} \\ \bar{Q}_{54} & \bar{Q}_{55} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \quad (18)$$

Finally, by comparing the results of these two different methods through eqn (1) we can obtain new SCC's with which an updated natural frequency can be calculated.

3 Least Squares Method Development

3.1 Displacement field basis

For this work we will develop a displacement field similar to that developed by Reddy (1984) [29], but which will be better suited for our needs in developing a piecewise continuous displacement field. We begin by assuming a symmetric, parabolic, transverse strain field of the form:

$$\gamma_{\alpha z} = \varphi_{\alpha}(a_0 + a_1 z^2), \quad (19)$$

where φ_{α} is a transverse shear strain, $\alpha = x, y$ and a_0 and a_1 are constants. If we force the transverse stress (strain) to go to zero at $z = \pm \frac{h}{2}$, we can eliminate the two constants. The result is substituted into the strain displacement relations for transverse strain and solved for $u_{\alpha, z}$. The result is integrated with respect to z resulting in:

$$u_{\alpha} = u_{\alpha 0} + \varphi_{\alpha} \left(z - \frac{4z^3}{3h^2} \right) - zw_{, \alpha} \quad (20)$$

We assume $w = w_o(x, y)$, a constant with respect to z , giving us the third displacement. A displacement field of this form was published by Bhimaraddi and Stevens [4] in 1984. Following the procedure as outlined by Lee et al (1990) [10] we can write a piecewise displacement field in the form

$$\begin{aligned}u^n &= u_o^1 + \sum_{k=1}^n P_k \varphi_x^1 + \alpha_n \varphi_x^1 \left(z - \frac{4z^3}{3h^2} \right) - zw_{, x} \\ v^n &= v_o^1 + \sum_{k=1}^n \bar{P}_k \varphi_y^1 + \alpha_n \varphi_y^1 \left(z - \frac{4z^3}{3h^2} \right) - zw_{, y} \\ w^n &= w_o\end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}P_j &= (z_j - 4z_j^3/3h^2) (\alpha_{j-1} - \alpha_j) & \bar{P}_j &= (z_j - 4z_j^3/3h^2) (\beta_{j-1} - \beta_j) \\ \varphi_x^n &= \alpha_n \varphi_x^1 & \varphi_y^n &= \beta_n \varphi_y^1 \\ \alpha_n &= \bar{C}_{44}^1 / \bar{C}_{44}^n & \beta_n &= \bar{C}_{55}^1 / \bar{C}_{55}^n\end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where \bar{C}_{44}^k and \bar{C}_{55}^k are the reduced stiffnesses for the k th layer, and here z_j is the distance to the bottom of j th layer. Superscripts n and 1 refer to the n th and first layers respectively.

At this time an important distinction is made in terminology. The three displacements given above in eqn (21) will be referred to as the *displacement fields*, while the five terms on the right hand side, $u_o^1, v_o^1, \varphi_x^1, \varphi_y^1$ and w , will be termed the *displacement functions*. This terminology will help make the following sections less confusing. The superscript, 1, will be dropped at this time, and reference to the first layer is understood.

Figure 1: Least Squares Element Domain

3.2 Finite element implementation

We begin by assuming the element domain shown in Figure 1 with a local η - ξ coordinate system as shown. This coordinate system is not unlike that of a standard isoparametric element. Within this domain we have displacements represented by eqns (21) in terms of five domain *displacement functions* u_o , v_o , w_o , φ_x and φ_y . Each of these functions is represented by an n term polynomial expansions in η and ξ with n unknown constants α_i . The expressions can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_o &= \alpha_1 + \alpha_2\eta + \alpha_3\xi + \alpha_4\eta^2 + \alpha_5\xi^2 + \alpha_6\eta\xi + \dots \\
 v_o &= \alpha_{n+1} + \alpha_{n+2}\eta + \alpha_{n+3}\xi + \alpha_{n+4}\eta^2 + \alpha_{n+5}\xi^2 + \alpha_{n+6}\eta\xi + \dots \\
 \varphi_x &= \alpha_{2n+1} + \alpha_{2n+2}\eta + \alpha_{2n+3}\xi + \alpha_{2n+4}\eta^2 + \alpha_{2n+5}\xi^2 + \alpha_{2n+6}\eta\xi + \dots \\
 \varphi_y &= \alpha_{3n+1} + \alpha_{3n+2}\eta + \alpha_{3n+3}\xi + \alpha_{3n+4}\eta^2 + \alpha_{3n+5}\xi^2 + \alpha_{3n+6}\eta\xi + \dots \\
 w &= \alpha_{4n+1} + \alpha_{4n+2}\eta + \alpha_{4n+3}\xi + \alpha_{4n+4}\eta^2 + \alpha_{4n+5}\xi^2 + \alpha_{4n+6}\eta\xi + \dots
 \end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

We first define

$$\{\mathbf{A}\}^T = [\mathbf{A}] = [1 \quad \eta \quad \xi \quad \eta\xi \quad \eta^2 \quad \xi^2 \quad \eta^2\xi \quad \eta\xi^2 \quad \eta^3 \quad \xi^3 \dots] \tag{24}$$

so that we can write the *displacement functions* in terms of α 's as:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} u_o \\ v_o \\ \varphi_x \\ \varphi_y \\ w \end{Bmatrix} = [\mathcal{A}'] \{\alpha\} \tag{25}$$

where

$$[\mathcal{A}'] = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{A} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \mathbf{A} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \mathbf{A} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \mathbf{A} \end{bmatrix} \tag{26}$$

and $\{\alpha\}$ is a column vector of all the α 's. Next, we add the local derivatives of w to these expressions to get:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{c} u_o \\ v_o \\ \varphi_x \\ \varphi_y \\ w \\ w_{,\eta} \\ w_{,\xi} \end{array} \right\} = [\mathcal{A}] \{\alpha\} \quad (27)$$

where

$$[\mathcal{A}] = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{A} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \mathbf{A} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \mathbf{A} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \mathbf{A} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \mathbf{A}_{,\eta} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \mathbf{A}_{,\xi} \end{bmatrix} \quad (28)$$

We now have everything we need to write the domain *displacement field* given in eqns (21) in terms of the domain functions given in eqns (23). The result is

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{c} u \\ v \\ w \end{array} \right\} = [I] [\mathcal{A}] \{\alpha\} \quad (29)$$

Here

$$[I] = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & c_1 & 0 & 0 & c_2 \Gamma_{11} & c_2 \Gamma_{12} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & \tilde{c}_1 & 0 & c_2 \Gamma_{21} & c_2 \Gamma_{22} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (30)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} c_1 &= \sum_{j=1}^k P_j + z\alpha_k - \frac{4z^3}{3h^2} \alpha_k & \tilde{c}_1 &= \sum_{j=1}^k \tilde{P}_j + z\beta_k - \frac{4z^3}{3h^2} \beta_k \\ c_2 &= -4z^3/3h^2 \end{aligned}$$

This now gives an expression for the domain *displacement field* in terms of the α 's . The next step is to relate eqn (27) to boundary *displacement functions* written in terms of nodal degrees of freedom.

The element domain shown in Figure 1 is first modified to include eight boundary nodes so that it resembles a standard quadratic isoparametric element. However, we define the nodal degrees of freedom as

$$\{\delta_i\}^T = [u_o \quad v_o \quad \varphi_x \quad \varphi_y \quad w \quad w_{,x} \quad w_{,y}] \quad i = 1, 2, 3, 4 \quad (31)$$

$$\{\delta_i\}^T = [u_o \quad v_o \quad \varphi_x \quad \varphi_y] \quad i = 5, 6, 7, 8 \quad (32)$$

giving the side nodes and the corner nodes different numbers of degrees of freedom for a total of 44 degrees of freedom per element. For future use, we define a vector containing all 44 degrees of freedom as:

$$\{\Delta\}^T = [\delta_1 \quad \delta_2 \quad \dots \quad \delta_8] \quad (33)$$

Along any edge of the element we have two corner nodes with 7 degrees of freedom and one side node with only four degrees of freedom, as described above. With this, u_o , v_o , φ_x and φ_y are defined by three quantities along the edge, one at each node. Any one of these four *displacement functions*, call it q , can be defined by a quadratic curve in the boundary variable s , which varies from -1.0 to $+1.0$ along any one of the four sides. See Figure 2. We can easily establish a second order equation for any of these four degrees of freedom. The function w , on the other hand, is defined by six nodal variables. We define $w_{,s}$ as the derivative of w tangent to the side in the direction of s , and $w_{,\eta}$ as the derivative

Figure 2: Variation of Nodal variable q along element side.

Figure 3: Variation of Nodal variable w along element side.

of w normal to the direction of s . See Figure 3. For a rectangular element aligned with the global x - y coordinate system these two derivatives correspond identically to either $w_{,x}$ or $w_{,y}$ depending upon which side one looks at. If the element is not straight sided or not aligned with the global coordinate system, the two derivatives will each be a linear combination of both $w_{,x}$ and $w_{,y}$ related through the standard Jacobian matrix. With this in mind, we see that w is defined by four variables, the two values of w and the two values $w_{,s}$. Thus, w can be fit by a cubic equation, making $w_{,s}$ quadratic. In addition, $w_{,n}$ is defined only by two points, one $w_{,n}$ at each end, thus making it vary linearly. It is significant that all functions, including $w_{,s}$ and $w_{,n}$, can be expressed along an edge of an element in terms of *only* the nodal values along that particular edge using simple equations. This will become an important fact to help insure compatibility from element to element.

The final step is to compile the curve fitting into a matrix format. It is convenient to write:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{c} u_o \\ v_o \\ \varphi_x \\ \varphi_y \\ w \\ w_{,x} \\ w_{,y} \end{array} \right\}_i = [\mathcal{F}]_i \{ \Delta \} \quad (34)$$

where the subscript i refers to the i th side of the element, and the matrix $[\mathcal{F}]$ contains the necessary terms from the linear, quadratic and cubic curve fitting as well as Jacobian terms relating the local differentials to the global ones.

At this point we have developed two different methods for finding expressions for the five *displacement functions*, as well as for the differentials of w . We first defined the functions anywhere in the element's domain in terms of unknown α 's (eqn (27)), as well as on the boundary in terms of the the

nodal degrees of freedom (eqn (34)). Let us refer to column vectors of these seven functions from each of these two equations as $\{\delta_\Omega\}$ and $\{\delta_\Gamma\}$ respectively. Here the symbols Ω and Γ correspond, of course, to domain and boundary. The vector $\{\delta_\Omega\}$ gives the seven functions in terms of the local coordinates, η and ξ , while $\{\delta_\Gamma\}$ gives them as functions of a boundary variable, s .

Next, we define a functional, I , as the integral of the square of the difference between the domain *displacement functions* evaluated on the boundary and the boundary *displacement functions* established from the nodal degrees of freedom. This is written as:

$$I = \int_{\Omega} (\{\delta_\Omega\}_\Gamma - \{\delta_\Gamma\})^2 dA \quad (35)$$

Substituting in the expressions from eqn (27) and eqn (34) the above equation becomes:

$$I = \int_{\Omega} ([A] \{\alpha\} - [\mathcal{F}]_i \{\Delta\})^2 dA \quad (36)$$

The functional I can now be minimized with respect to the α 's to obtain the expression

$$\frac{\partial I}{\partial \alpha} = \int_{\Omega} \left([A]^T [A] \{\alpha\} - [A]^T [\mathcal{F}]_i \{\Delta\} \right) dA = 0 \quad (37)$$

(The constant 2 has been divided out.) Upon performing this integration, the expression can be solved for the α 's³. The result is

$$\{\alpha\} = \left([A]^T [A] \right)^{-1} [A]^T [\mathcal{F}] \{\Delta\} \quad (38)$$

or

$$\{\alpha\} = [H] \{\Delta\} \quad (39)$$

where

$$[H] = \left([A]^T [A] \right)^{-1} [A]^T [\mathcal{F}] \quad (40)$$

This result is the basis for the Least Squares Element. The unknowns, (the α 's) are chosen in such a manner as to *force* these functions to match those on the boundary which are determined from the nodal degrees of freedom. Thus, compatibility is met in a least squared sense.

With eqn (39) and eqn (27) we can update eqn (29) to be

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{c} u \\ v \\ w \end{array} \right\} = [T] [A] [H] \{\Delta\} \quad (41)$$

With eqn (41) we now have an expression for the element *displacement field*. This field represents the *displacement field* already in terms of the element local coordinate system. The role usually performed by shape functions has already been filled directly for the Least Squares element. The strain field, or any desired differential field for that matter, is found by directly differentiating $[A]$ in eqn (41). In addition, all three variables, w , $w_{,x}$ and $w_{,y}$, will remain compatible along common element boundaries. As a result, so will u and v . The remainder of the finite element implementation follows standard procedures, and will not be presented here for the sake of brevity.

4 Numerical Results

The finite element programs for the PC technique and the LS method were implemented in FORTRAN on a CYBER 990 computer. The analysis results for only two laminates will be presented here. They are for a $[0/90/90/0]$ crossply made from Material I, and a laminate composed of two different materials

³Note: To keep the number of symbols used to a minimum, the same symbols are used after the integration to represent the variables. The difference is understood.

Figure 4: Method Comparison of Percent Error in Natural Frequency -vs- Anisotropy Ratio. [0/90/90/0], Material I, $b/h = 5$, $a/b = 1$, Simply Supported, 4×4 Quarter Plate Mesh

(hybrid). (See Table 1.) The ply layout of the hybrid laminate considered in this analysis is [45/-45/0/90/45/-45/0/90] $_{AS}$. The middle eight layers are Material II, and the top four and bottom four layers are Material III. This laminate was chosen to match that analyzed by Noor and Burton (1990) [22]. Results (presented in Table 2) for the crossply laminate are compared to those obtained from a simplified higher order theory (SHOT) obtained from Phan and Reddy (1985) [27]. Table 3 gives the results for the hybrid case which are compared to the SHOT as well as a discrete layer and simplified discrete layer theory from Noor and Burton [22]. All data is for simply supported plates. Data is also presented graphically in Figures 4 and 5. With the PC technique it was difficult to calculate the SCC's near the edges of the plate or anywhere where the transverse shear stresses were small. The integration through the thickness of the plate relies upon the addition of many numbers, which results in inaccuracies if the numbers are small. The coefficients themselves are then found by dividing a small number by another. The result is likely to be inaccurate, so the SCC's should be calculated from the data found surrounding an area in the plate where the stresses are relatively high. In addition, a finer mesh is needed to accurately calculate the SCC's than is required for natural frequency convergence. This fact presents a problem for cases where lack of symmetry requires full plate modeling. In order to get accurate SCC's the computational time and storage requirements can quickly become large. The coefficients calculated in this study compared well to those found by Noor [21],[22].

The behavior of the LS element requires more investigation than the standard isoparametric Mindlin

Table 1: Material Properties.

MATERIAL	E_L/E_T	G_{LT}/E_T	G_{TT}/E_T	ν_{LT}	ν_{TT}
I	? [†]	0.6	.5	.25	.25
II	4.46	.566	.395	.415	.49
III*	11.49	.566	.28	.38	.49

*For this material: $E_T = 1.14E_{T(II)}$ and $\rho = 0.846\rho_{(II)}$

[†] Indicates variable ratio.

Table 2: Natural Frequency Results -vs- Anisotropy Ratio.
 $[0/90/90/0]$, Material I, $b/h = 5$, $a/b = 1$,
 $\omega_n = (\omega b^2/h) (\rho/E_2)^{1/2}$, Simply supported

E_L/E_T	Exact	SHOT	PC	LS
3	6.6815	6.5597	6.5740	6.5378
10	8.2103	8.2718	8.2697	8.2515
20	9.5603	9.5263	9.5073	9.5164
30	10.272	10.272	10.212	10.275
40	10.752	10.787	10.644	10.804

Table 3: Natural Frequency Results -vs- Thickness ratio.
 16 Layer Hybrid, Material I & II, $a/b = 1$,
 $\omega_n = \omega (\rho h^2/E_2)^{1/2}$, Simply supported

h/b	Exact	SHOT	Discrete Layer	Simplified Discrete Layer	PC	LS
0.01	0.001354	0.001364	0.001353	0.0013712	0.001359	0.001349
0.05	0.03290	-	-	-	0.032905	0.03281
0.10	0.1217	-	-	-	0.12155	0.12163
0.15	0.2463	-	-	-	0.24556	0.24670
0.20	0.3893	0.39693	0.38881	0.40469	0.38771	0.39108
0.25	0.5405	-	-	-	0.53724	0.54450
0.30	0.6946	0.71611	0.69380	0.72866	0.69039	0.70172

element used for the PC technique. The element is non-conforming in the sense that it is not free from gaps⁴ between elements. However, the gaps are minimized in a least squares sense. In the LS method the normal derivative of the out-of-plane displacement along an edge of an element was forced to be linear while the tangential derivative was quadratic. With *displacement functions* of sufficient order, these requirements can be enforced. Thus, the gaps, which are minimized by enforcing these requirements, should tend to zero as the number of elements increases. However, in minimizing the gaps, the element is *warped* into a shape not commensurate with the true solution. Thus, the element may start out soft due to the presence of gaps, but become stiffer as the number of elements increases. It may also converge to a slightly stiffer solution. Figure 6 shows a typical convergence trend for the LS element.

5 Conclusions and Recommendations

The PC and LS methods provide accurate yet computationally efficient means to solve thick LFRCP problems. The PC technique extends the effectiveness of the simple Mindlin plate element to a performance level much higher than previously thought. The LS method provides a simple, yet accurate, tool to solve the C^1 continuity problem. With this capability, a simplified, piecewise continuous theory utilizing a higher order basis can be implemented into the finite element method with complexity similar to a first order theory. The results of this research have shown that accurate results can be achieved for thick composite laminates without turning to complex and computationally intensive methods. More effort should be expended into solving the LFRCP problem through simple, yet accurate means.

For complete details into either of these methods, as well as for more information on stress calculations, stability analysis, prestressed vibrations and laminate ply angle and stacking sequence effects see Kouri (1991) [9].

⁴The word *gap* is used loosely to refer to both gaps and overlaps.

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Figure 5: Method Comparison of Percent Error in Natural Frequency -vs- Thickness Ratio. 16 layer Hybrid- Materials II & III, $a/b = 1$, Simply Supported, 4×4 Quarter Plate Mesh

Figure 6: Least Squares Element Convergence. 16 Layer Hybrid- Materials II & III, simply supported, $a/b = 1$, quarter plate model.

References

- [1] Naiyar Alam and N. T. Asnani. Vibration and damping analysis of a multilayered cylindrical shell, part i: Theoretical analysis. *American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics Journal*, 22(6):803–810, June 1984.
- [2] Naiyar Alam and N. T. Asnani. Vibration and damping analysis of a multilayered cylindrical shell, part ii: Numerical results. *American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics Journal*, 22(7):975–981, July 1984.
- [3] E. J. Barbero and J. N. Reddy. An accurate determination of stresses in thick laminates using a generalized plate theory. *International Journal of Numerical Methods in Engineering*, 29:1–14, 1990.
- [4] A. Bhimaraddi and L. K Stevens. A higher order theory for free vibration of orthotropic, homogeneous, and laminated rectangular plates. *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, 51:195–198, March 1984.
- [5] T. Kant and B.N.Pandya. A simple finite element formulation of a higher-order theory for unsymmetrically laminated composite plates. *Composite Structures*, 9:215–246, 1988.
- [6] T. Kant and Mallikarjuna. Vibrations of unstymmetrically laminated plates analyzed by using a higher order theory with a C^0 finite element formulation. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, 134(1):1–16, 1989.
- [7] T. Kant, R.V. Ravichandran, B. N. Pandya, and Mallikarjuna. Finite element transient dynamic analysis of isotropic and fibre reinforced composite plates using a higher-order theory. *Composite Structures*, 9:319–342, 1988.
- [8] A. A. Khdeir. Free vibration and buckling of unsymmetric cross-ply laminated plates using a refined theory. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, 128(3):377–395, 1989.
- [9] Jeffrey V. Kouri. *Improved Finite Element Analysis of Thick Laminated Composite Plates by the Predictor Corrector Technique and Approximation of C^1 Continuity with a New Least Squares Element*. PhD thesis, Georgia Institute of Technology, 1991.
- [10] K. H. Lee, N. R. Senthilnathan, S. P. Lim, and S. T. Chow. An improved zig-zag model for the bending of laminated composite plates. *Composite Structures*, 15:137–148, 1990.
- [11] S. P. Lim, K. H. Lee, S. T. Chow, and N. R. Senthilnathan. Linear and nonlinear bending of shear-deformable plates. *Computers and Structures*, 30(4):945–952, 1988.
- [12] K. H. Lo, R.M. Christensen, and E.M. Wu. A high-order theory of plate deformation, Part 1: Homogeneous plates. *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, 44:663–668, Dec 1977.
- [13] K. H. Lo, R.M. Christensen, and E.M. Wu. A high-order theory of plate deformation, Part 2: Laminated plates. *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, 44:669–676, Dec 1977.
- [14] Mallikarjuna and T. Kant. Free vibration of symmetrically laminated plates using a higher-order theory with finite element technique. *International Journal of Numerical Methods in Engineering*, 28:1875–1889, 1989.
- [15] A. S. Mawenya and J. D. Davies. Finite element bending analysis of multilayer plates. *International Journal of Numerical Methods in Engineering*, 8:215–225, 1974.
- [16] J. T. Mottram. High-order analysis of generally symmetrical laminated plates under transverse loading. *Composite Structures*, 12:211–237, 1989.
- [17] A. V. Krishna Murty. Higher order theory for vibrations of thick plates. *American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics Journal*, 15(12):1823–1824, December 1977.
- [18] A. V. Krishna Murty. Flexure of composite plates. *Composite Structures*, 7:161–177, 1987.
- [19] A. V. Krishna Murty and S. Vellaichamy. On higher order shear deformation theory of laminated composite panels. *Composite Structures*, 8:247–270, 1987.

- [20] R. B. Nelson and D. R. Lorch. A refined theory for laminated orthotropic plates. *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, 41(1):177–183, March 1974.
- [21] A. K. Noor and W. Scott Burton. Stress and free vibration analyses of multilayered composite plates. *Composite Structures*, 11:183–204, 1989.
- [22] A. K. Noor and W. Scott Burton. Assessment of computational models for multilayered anisotropic plates. *Composite Structures*, 14:233–265, 1990.
- [23] A. K. Noor and J. M. Peters. A posteriori estimates for shear correction factors in multi-layered composite cylinders. *Journal of Engineering Mechanics*, 115(6):1225–1244, June 1989.
- [24] N. J. Pagano. Exact solutions for composite laminates in cylindrical bending. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 3:398–411, July 1969.
- [25] N. J. Pagano. Exact solutions for rectangular bidirectional composites and sandwich plates. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 4:20–34, January 1970.
- [26] B. N. Pandya and T. Kant. Finite element analysis of laminated composite plates using a higher-order displacement model. *Composite Science and Technology*, 32:137–155, 1988.
- [27] N. D. Phan and J. N. Reddy. Analysis of laminated composite plates using a higher-order shear deformation theory. *International Journal of Numerical Methods in Engineering*, 21:2201–2219, 1985.
- [28] J. N. Reddy. A refined nonlinear theory of plates with transverse shear deformation. *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, 20(9/10):881–896, 1984.
- [29] J. N. Reddy. A simple higher-order theory for laminated composite plates. *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, 51:745–752, December 1984.
- [30] J. N. Reddy, E. J. Barbero, and J. L. Teply. A plate bending element based on a generalized laminate plate theory. *International Journal of Numerical Methods in Engineering*, 28:2275–2292, 1989.
- [31] J. N. Reddy and N. D. Phan. Stability and vibration of isotropic, orthotropic and laminated plates according to a higher-order shear deformation theory. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, 98(2):157–170, 1985.
- [32] M. Di Sciuva. An improved shear-deformation theory for moderately thick multilayered anisotropic shells and plates. *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, 54:589–596, September 1987.
- [33] N. R. Senthilnathan, S. P. Lim, K. H. Lee, and S. T. Chow. Vibration of laminated orthotropic plates using a simplified higher-order deformation theory. *Composite Structures*, 10:211–229, 1988.
- [34] S. Srinivas. A refined analysis of composite laminates. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, 30(4):495–507, 1973.

